

WayScience

2nd International Scientific
and Practical Internet Conference

«Future Healthcare:
Innovations, Advances and Progress»
ISBN 978-617-8293-13-0

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Editorial board of International Electronic Scientific and Practical Journal «WayScience»
(ISSN 2664-4819 (Online))

The editorial board of the Journal is not responsible for the content of the papers and may not share the author's opinion.

Future Healthcare: Innovations, Advances and Progress: Proceedings of the 2nd International Scientific and Practical Internet Conference, June 15-16, 2023. FOP Marenichenko V.V., Dnipro, Ukraine, 165 p.

ISBN 978-617-8293-13-0

2nd International Scientific and Practical Internet Conference "Future Healthcare: Innovations, Advances and Progress" is devoted to finding ways to the best conditions of health, life and well-being of human.

Topics:

- future of health sphere;
- future of life sphere;
- future of well-being sphere;
- other general and special issues (the author notes).

Dnipro, Ukraine – 2023

STUDY OF PALLIATIVE PATIENTS' QUALITY OF LIFE AS AN INDICATOR OF HEALTH CARE ORGANIZATION QUALITY

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Palliative and hospice care (PHC) is intended for patients with terminal illnesses and their family members. The quality of PHC organization is an indicator of the development of national healthcare systems and social standards level [1; 2]. Ukraine belongs to the group of countries in the world with separate specialized PHC institutions, the work of which does not have signs of systematic organization at the state level. Approximately 190–227 thousand adults and 45–61 thousand children need for PHC annually. But this need is only partially satisfied [3; 4]. In the conditions of a long-term reform of the health care system, Ukraine is trying to develop an outpatient PHC component of using mobile palliative teams and inpatients at home. However, 3/4 of palliative patients who need psychological, spiritual and social support receive it mainly from relatives, and not from psychologists, social workers and clergy [3]. A significant problem of the PHC organization is the lack of a national mechanism for calculating the need for these types of assistance, which makes it difficult to finance their provision by the National Health Service of Ukraine.

According to our own calculation, the minimum and optimal number of required palliative departments varies between 80–260 for adults and 20–70 for children, beds – (1,100–1,400) and (580–630), mobile services – (260–520) and (60–400), inpatient doctors – (215–285) and (120–50), inpatient nurses – (600–1,700) and (100–1,000), doctors of field teams – (500– 2,000) and (120–1,580), nurses of mobile teams – (520–6,200) and (120–4,750), respectively [5]. However, it is clear that the calculation mechanism needs to be improved, and the collection of the necessary statistics needs to be more accurate [6; 7].

Studying the subjective opinion of patients regarding PHC can be an additional reference point for adjusting measures to improve these types of care. For this purpose, it is possible to use both standard methods of studying the quality of life (the SF-36 questionnaire) and their modifications according to the profile of patients receiving PHC. When calculating the need for PHC, we established a list of such diseases. For adults, it includes such diseases as malignant neoplasms, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, kidney diseases, rheumatoid arthritis, fibrosis and cirrhosis of the liver, tuberculosis and HIV/AIDS; for children – congenital malformations, infantile cerebral palsy, phenylketonuria, cystic fibrosis, mucopolysaccharidoses, inflammatory diseases of the central nervous system, severe perinatal conditions, HIV/AIDS, tuberculosis, malignant neoplasms, diabetes, cardiovascular diseases and chronic hepatitis.

The list of questions of the standard SF-36 questionnaire includes questions about self-assessment of the state of one's health (as of now and in comparison with the last year), questions about the ability to perform physical exercises and everyday tasks with loads, about emotional state, mood and physical pain. The advantage of the standard technique lies in its general recognition and experience of use by many researchers, but the disadvantage is the focus on patients who are able to move freely. But many palliative patients are bedridden. Therefore, the direction of our future research is to modify the questionnaire not only for the list of diseases, but also for the palliative state of patients with these diseases.

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